

Quantum Mechanics, Classical Phase Space and Free Particles

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There have been a number of derivations of the Schrodinger equation from a classical statistical scenario (1) using a joint classical probability function $F(p,x,t)$. A main feature of these approaches is to use $0=dF/dt= dF/dt (\text{partial}) + dF/dx p/m + dF/dp (-dV/dx)$. Thus, these scenarios focus on force and also make use of classical density. Furthermore, derivatives of density are linked to dynamics i.e. to $-dV/dx$. Towards the end of these derivations, classical density is set equal to $W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$ without apparent motivation. Nevertheless, the approaches do lead to the Schrodinger equation.

In some previous notes, we argued that the physics of the problem is contained in $W(x)$. In this note, we particularly point out that a notion of a free particle is directly linked to $W(x)$ if one wishes to have spatial derivatives linked to dynamics which seems to be a main focus of these classical statistical approaches. Even if density is constant i.e. has zero spatial derivatives, one may have another function, linked to density, which contains the dynamics of a free particle. This function may be of a statistical nature and may allow for the construction of an ensemble of free particles (just as in classical physics)

In this note, we consider these ideas and link them to a particular derivation of the Schrodinger equation given in (1) based on a Wigner-Weyl (or Wigner-Moyal) transformation.

Wigner-Weyl (Wigner-Moyal) Transformation

In this section, we give a brief description of the statistical phase space approach used to obtain the Schrodinger equation in (1). It links a kind of spatial density to $F(p,x,t)$ (a classical joint probability density) and focuses on derivatives of this quantity in order to obtain a $-dV/dx$ term. Thus, it focuses on acceleration and not a free particle.

The Wigner-Weyl transformation is defined in (1) as:

$$\langle x_1 | T(F) | y \rangle = \text{Integral } dp \exp(i(x-y)p) F((x_1+y)/2, p, t) \quad \hbar=1 \quad ((1))$$

The authors of (1) call $\langle x_1 | T(F) | y \rangle = \text{density}(x,y) = D(x,y)$ i.e. a kind of spatial density where $\text{density}(x,x) = \text{spatial density}$ and focus on:

$$X_1 = x+d/2 \quad \text{and} \quad y = x-d/2 \quad \text{where } d \text{ is very small} \quad ((2))$$

Then the Wigner-Weyl transformation becomes:

$$D(x_1,y) = \text{Integral } dp \exp(ip d) F(p,x,t) \quad ((3)) \quad \text{where } D \text{ is a kind of density i.e. } D(x,x) = \text{spatial density.}$$

$$\text{Use is made of: } 0 = dF/dt = dF/dt (\text{partial}) + p/m dF/dx - dV/dx dF/dp \quad ((4))$$

where $V(x)$ is the potential. ((4)) is then multiplied by $\exp(i p d)$ and integrated over p to obtain:

$$-dD/dt (\text{partial}) + i/m d/dx d/d(d) D - i dV/dx d D = 0 \quad ((5)) \quad \text{where } D(x+d/2, x-d/2)$$

(The authors of (1) also use a parameter l which disappears so we do not use it here.)

Thus, one may see that ((5)) is based on $-dV/dx$ or force and involves derivatives of spatial density. For a free particle one might note that $d/dx d/d(d) D = 0$, but $D(x,x)$ would be a constant in such a case.

Finally, $D(y,y1)$ is set equal to $W^*(y)W(y1)$ ((6)) without clear motivation. Next,

$$W(y) \text{ is written as } R(y,t) \exp[i S(y,t)] \quad ((7))$$

W^*W , written in terms of R and S is inserted into ((5)) and real and imaginary terms collected. The imaginary part yields:

$$d/dx \{ 1/2m (dS/dx)(dS/dx) + V + dS/dt (\text{partial}) - 1/(2mR) d/dx d/dx R \} = 0 \quad ((8))$$

with the expression inside the $\{ \}$ being the Schrodinger equation.

Focus on Free Particles

The derivation above centers on the classical joint probability density $F(x,p,t)$ which applies to an ensemble rather than to a free particle. Furthermore, derivatives of this joint probability lead to $-dV/dx$ which implies acceleration which is also not part of the scenario of a free particle.

It seems, however, that quantum mechanical features such as a two-slit interference pattern pertain to free particles which interact with a potential at the two-slits. Thus, quantum mechanics should be present already at the level of the free particle which is not acted on by a force.

The statistical approach given above focuses on linking derivatives of spatial density to a force. Then, density is set equal to W^*W and so spatial derivatives act on W^* and W and these become linked to kinetic energy because an overall d/dx is removed from $-dV/dx$ and other terms. Thus, ultimately it is the function $W(x,t)$ and its spatial derivatives which contain dynamical information. Given that this is the case, one may postulate a function whose derivatives yield dynamical information p, pp for a free particle. If this function is statistical, it should be linked to a constant spatial density. We have argued in previous notes that $\exp(ipx)$ is a candidate and have shown that one may create a statistical picture based on an ensemble of $\exp(ipx)$'s in the presence of a potential $V(x)$. This leads to the same results as the $F(x,p,t)$ approach, but places the free particle wavefunction $W(x,t)=\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ at the forefront and creates a statistical scenario from an ensemble of $\exp(ipx)$'s i.e. free particles just as in classical statistical mechanics.

Bound Particle Considerations and the Wigner-Weyl Transformation

If $W(x)=\exp(ipx)$ for a free particle and W^*W is density then $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$ for an ensemble in a potential $V(x)$ and W^*W may be postulated as spatial density. For a bound scenario W is real and one may consider the Wigner-Weyl transformation used in (1) i.e.

$$D(x+d/2, x-d/2) = W(x+d/2, x-d/2)W^*(x+d/2, x-d/2) = \int dp F(p,x) \exp(ipd) \quad ((9))$$

Expanding to second order in the small parameter d gives:

$$W(x)W(x) + 0 + dd/4 \{ -dW/dx dW/dx + d/dx d/dx W \} \quad ((10))$$

One may also expand the RHS of ((9)) i.e.

$$D(x,x) + 0 - \frac{1}{2} dd \int F(p,x) pp \quad ((10))$$

Given that it is derivatives of F which are linked to dynamics:

$$dd/4 \ d/dx \{ -dW/dx dW/dx + d/dx d/dx W \} = -\frac{1}{2} dd \int dp dF/dx pp \quad ((11))$$

For $0=dF/dt = dF/dt (\text{partial}) + dF/dx p/m + dF/dp (-dV/dx)$ with $dF/dt (\text{partial}) = 0$ the RHS of ((11)) becomes:

$$-\frac{1}{2} dd \int dp dV/dx dF/dp p \quad ((12)) \text{ which should integrate to } -\frac{1}{2} dd dV/dx D(x,x)$$

From the time-independent Schrodinger equation, $-dV/dx D(x,x) = d/dx (-1/2m d/dx dW/dx / W)$

Thus, $-1/2m d/dx WW \{ -dW/dx dW/dx + Wd/dx d/dx W \}$ from the LHS of ((11)) should be equivalent to $-WW d/dx KE(x)$ and it is. This leads to two different pictures.

The first is a picture of a distribution of free particle $\exp(ipx)$ at each W point x such that:

$$E = V(x) + \{ \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) pp/2m \exp(ipx) \} / \{ \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx) \} \quad ((12))$$

The second scenario is to think in terms of the average velocity field i.e.

$v(x) = -i d/dx W / mW$ and $d/dx v(x) = -i d/dx (dW/dx / W)$ which when multiplied by WW is very similar to ((11)). In such a case:

$$-1/2m \{ -dW/dx dW/dx + Wd/dx d/dx W \} = -m/2 \text{ density } v(x)v(x) + \text{density } KE(x) \quad ((13))$$

Thus, there is also an expectation value $\langle W \text{ Operator } W \rangle$ picture which is the usual one considered in quantum mechanics.

Conclusion

In conclusion, a number of papers in the literature derive the Schrodinger equation from a classical statistical scenario using $F(p,x,t)$ the classical joint probability density. Derivatives of this function are taken and linked to p/m and $-dV/dx$ and also: $\int dp F(p,x,t)$ is linked to spatial density. Towards the end of these derivations, spatial density is set $= W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$ without apparent motivation. In doing so, spatial derivatives of $W(x,t)$ become related to dynamical quantities such as $KE(x)$. Thus, we argue that the quantum mechanical information is really contained in $W(x,t)$. In this note, we stress that for a free particle, the density is constant and there is no $-dV/dx$, so it seems one needs to consider a statistical function whose spatial derivatives are linked to dynamics, but this function needs to also be linked to constant spatial density. This yields $\exp(ipx)$ from which one may create an ensemble $W(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ to deal with systems with a potential using the same strategy as classical statistical mechanics. This approach yields the same result as the $F(x,p,t)$ approaches, but puts the wavefunction at the forefront from the beginning and focuses on the free particle wavefunction.

References

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